

Inca

also known as “Inka”

By Darryl Wilkinson, Dartmouth College

Entry tags: Inkas, Animist, Andes, Peru, Quechuan, Religious Group, State Religion, Ancestral Worship, Language, Aymaran

The Incas were an Indigenous Andean ethnic group who resided in the Cusco region of the central Andes (what is now southern Peru) during the late pre-colonial period. Although originally an agricultural society that occupied a small number of settlements in the Cusco region, the Incas rapidly expanded their territory from around 1350 CE onwards. Eventually, they created the largest empire ever seen in the ancient Americas, spanning over 3,000 kilometers from north to south and encompassing a total population of about 12 million people. Only a small fraction of the empire's inhabitants would have been considered ethnically Inca. In addition, a number of closely allied ethnic groups in the Cusco region were granted the status of Incas-by-privilege; meaning they were afforded a social and political status that was similar to the Incas themselves. The main language of the Inca Empire was Quechua (specifically the Southern Peruvian variety), although due to the large scale of the polity, numerous other languages were spoken within its territory. However, it is likely the pre-imperial Incas originally spoke another language, perhaps a version of Aymara, and only adopted Quechua as a lingua franca during the process of imperial expansion. In many respects, the religious and ritual practices of the Incas were broadly similar to those of other central Andean peoples during the late pre-colonial period. Interactions with mummified ancestors were a particularly important part of Inca ceremonial life. Also vital were ritual relationships with landscape features like lakes, springs, bedrock outcrops and mountains, as well as various celestial bodies, especially the sun and moon. Perhaps the most distinctive feature of Inca religion was the vast scale on which it was organized, and the highly centralized and hierarchical character it exhibited within an imperial context.

Date Range: 1350 CE - 1533 CE

Region: Inca Empire

Region tags: Andes

The Inca Empire at its maximum extent in CE 1532

Status of Participants:

✓ Elite ✓ Religious Specialists ✓ Non-elite (common people, general populace)

Sources

Print sources for understanding this subject:

- Source 1: Cobo, Bernabé. 1990 [1653] *Inca Religion and Customs*. Translated and edited by Roland Hamilton. Austin: University of Texas Press.
- Source 2: Molina, Cristóbal de. 2011 [1575]. *Account fo the Fables and Rites of the Incas*. Translated by Brian Bauer, Vania Smith-Oka and Gabriel E. Cantarutti. Austin: University of Texas Press.
- Source 3: Diez de Betanzos, Juan. 1996 [1557]. *Narrative of the Incas*. Translated and edited by Roland Hamilton and Dana Buchanan. Austin: University of Texas Press.

Notes: These are among the most important colonial-era accounts of Inca religion written by Spanish chroniclers.

Online sources for understanding this subject:

– Source 1 URL: <https://artsandculture.google.com/story/jwWRECr11WMRIQ>

Notes: This link is to an online exhibition of Inca artifacts related to religious matters, provided by the Museo Machu Picchu (Machu Picchu Museum)

Relevant online primary textual corpora (original languages and/or translations):

– Source 1 URL: <https://www.kb.dk/permalink/2006/poma/info/en/frontpage.htm>

Notes: This link is an online digital facsimile of the 1615 letter written to the Spanish Crown by the Indigenous Andean chronicler Guaman Poma de Ayala. It provides extensive information (mainly in Spanish, with some Quechua portions) on the history, religion and customs of the Inca Empire.

General Variables

Membership/Group Interactions

Are other religious groups in cultural contact with target religion:

– Yes

Notes: The Incas conquered a large number of Andean societies during the process of their imperial expansion, thereby incorporating the religious traditions of many other peoples into their domain. The populations of the central Andean highlands exhibited religious practices that were often very similar to the Incas, especially with regards to the veneration of mummified ancestors; albeit on a much smaller scale. However, the Pacific coasts had their own distinct religious traditions that the Incas sought to integrate into their politico-religious framework. By far, the most important religious center on the coast was Pachacamac, located just south of the modern city of Lima. This site was a massive pyramidal complex made of adobe, covering an area of just under 600 hectares. Its focal point was a powerful oracle, in the form of a carved wooden column, housed in an adobe structure near the summit. The prominence of Pachacamac as an oracular center long predated the rise of the Incas, by as much as a thousand years or so. The Incas conquered Pachacamac and the local Ychsma peoples around 1470 CE, and they subsequently renovated and expanded the Pachacamac complex. The Incas continued the veneration of the Pachacamac deity, but also added a shrine dedicated to their own chief deity (the sun, called Inti). Under the Incas, it seems the number of pilgrims visiting the Pachacamac oracular center may have actually increased.

Does the religious group have a general process/system for assigning religious affiliation:

– No

Notes: As with other Indigenous societies of the pre-colonial Americas, religion is not a category that would have been recognized by the peoples of the Inca Empire. What appears as religious practice from a modern perspective, would have been fully interwoven with the political and economic spheres. As such, there were no distinctive religious affiliations or groups to which one could belong.

Does the religious group actively proselytize and recruit new members:

– No

Notes: As with other Indigenous societies of the pre-colonial Americas, religion is not a category that would have been recognized by the peoples of the Inca Empire. What appears as religious practice from a modern perspective, would have been fully interwoven with the political and economic spheres. There is therefore no direct equivalent to proselytization or religious conversion. The expansion of the Inca Empire would have forced certain groups to participate in its religious or ritual activities to some degree, although this process would have been indistinguishable from the political and economic integration of subject populations. Moreover, expansion of the empire would almost exclusively have been experienced collectively, as entire lineages or urban communities were brought under Inca control; incorporation into the empire did not target individuals.

Does the religion have official political support

– Yes

Notes: There is no meaningful distinction between the Inca state and the Inca religion. All expressions of Inca religion were therefore integrated with and supported by the state and its political apparatus. Whereas other ancient empires might have been officially Christian, Muslim or Buddhist (etc.), this explicit nomination of an official religion implies that alternative possibilities were conceivable. In the Inca context, however, there was no imaginable religion except the Inca religion, in part because the Inca religion was fundamentally incorporative instead of exclusive. The religious practices of non-Inca societies were not rejected by the Incas, but rather subsumed under the imperial religion.

Is there a conception of apostasy in the religious group:

– No

Notes: Participation in Inca religion was fundamentally a question of practice, rather than explicitly expressed beliefs, doctrines or creeds. Moreover, participation in religion in the ancient Andes was generally a function of one's membership in kin groups or residential communities (i.e. towns or cities), not something that was manifest at the level of the individual. Religion was not an expression of personal choice or conscience in such contexts, and there is therefore no equivalent to apostasy. Certain ethnic groups did resist the Incas, thereby rejecting their religious practices, although this was as much a political rebellion as an act of religious refusal.

Size and Structure

Number of adherents of religious group within sample region (estimated population, numerical):

– Estimated population, numeric: 12000000

Notes: Participation in the state religion of the Inca Empire was, to some degree, unavoidable for the entire imperial population of around 12 million people. However, more complex and elite forms of adherence would have been restricted to the 150,000 or so ethnic Incas and their closest allies.

Number of adherents of religious group within sample region (% of sample region population, numerical):

– Estimated population, percentage of sample region: 100

Notes: The religious and ritual practices of the Inca Empire would have involved the entire population, albeit to varying degrees, depending on the specific practice or activity in question.

Scripture

Does the religious group have scriptures:

Scripture is a generic term used to designate revered texts that are considered particularly authoritative and sacred relative to other texts. Strictly speaking, it refers to written texts, but there are also “oral scriptures” (e.g. the Vedas of India).

– No

Notes: The Inca recorded information using *kipu* (or *quipu*); complex artifacts comprised of multiple knotted cords, made from either wool or cotton. The ability of modern scholars to decipher the surviving 1000+ *kipu* is limited, although it seems a wide range of information was recorded through them, including censuses, tax records, historical accounts, genealogies and perhaps even more literary works, like poetry. However, there is no evidence that any *kipu* was ever used to record a religious or cosmological text that could be seen as analogous to the written scriptures found in other parts of the world.

Architecture, Geography

Is monumental religious architecture present:

– Yes

Notes: The Inca Empire constructed many religious monuments within its territory. The city of Cusco (the imperial capital) was centered on a temple complex called the Coricancha (or Qorikancha), which exhibited a series of large monumental walls and terraces, enclosing an interior courtyard and associated rooms. This may have been the most important religious architectural construction in the Inca world; it housed the most important earthly manifestation of the deified sun, a golden object called *Punchao*, as well as other celestial entities. In addition, on a hill overlooking the capital lies the massive complex of Sacsayhuaman (or Saqsaywaman). Some of the huge cyclopean masonry blocks used to build this site weigh as much as 100 tons, and although it probably fulfilled political and military functions as well, there is no question that ceremonialism and ritual were key aspects of Sacsayhuaman's overall design. Beyond the capital itself, there were many shrine complexes, referred to as *huacas* (or *wak'a*) in Quechua. Most of these shrines were focused on water sources (e.g. springs) and bedrock outcrops, which were elaborated via monumental masonry constructions. The natural landscape features that comprised the *huacas* were understood as sentient, living beings and were the focus of a substantial portion of the state rituals sponsored by the Inca Empire. Important examples of such sites include Tambo Machay and Kenko Grande, both located immediately to the north of Cusco. Also within a 100 kilometer radius of Cusco, there were many royal estates, of which the most famous example is Machu Picchu. These estates included palaces for the Inca aristocracy, alongside numerous *huacas* in the form of modified springs and rock outcrops. Although it is fair to say that the most impressive examples of religious monuments are concentrated in and around the capital, there are still multiple examples from farther afield. A common example are the monumental constructions called *ushnus*. Many important *ushnus* took the form of a stone-built platform in the center of a public plaza, which could sometimes be quite large and elaborate. For instance, the *ushnu* at Vilcashuamán in Ayacucho was a large “pyramidal” masonry structure with at least four tiers that reached some 8 meters in height.

Are there different types of religious monumental architecture:

– Yes

↳ Tombs:

– No

Notes: Although there may have been one or two possible exceptions, monumental tombs were not a typical feature of Inca architecture. Across the Inca Empire, it seems most of the dead were buried in pits, clay capsules or shaft tombs, or somewhat less frequently, inside ceramic vessels—with little evidence of any standardized form of mortuary practice. Some Inca sites, such as Machu Picchu, include structures that have been interpreted as places where royal mummies were kept, although this is not certain. Standalone mausolea, however, are mostly absent from the Inca context.

↳ Cemeteries:

– No

Notes: Although there are Inca cemeteries, these generally lack any significant monumental elaboration.

↳ Temples:

– Yes

Notes: Major temple complexes existed throughout the Inca Empire. The city of Cusco (the imperial capital) was centered on a temple complex called the Coricancha (or Qorikancha), which exhibited a series of large monumental walls and terraces, enclosing an interior courtyard and associated rooms. Another massive temple complex dedicated to the creator deity Viracocha was constructed at Raqchi, about 100 kilometers southeast of Cusco. Alongside its various architectural components, which included storehouses and lodging facilities for visitors, was an artificial lake; probably the ceremonial focus of the complex. It was very common for Inca temples to incorporate landscape features such as rock outcrops and bodies of water, which were often the primary manifestations of divine beings.

↳ Altars:

– Yes

Notes: Ushnu platforms could be interpreted as altars. In the Inca context, the term ushnu is often applied to ceremonial architectural platforms, which were sometimes located inside major settlements or towns, as well as in remote locales throughout the wider landscape (such as on hilltops). There is substantial archaeological and ethnohistorical evidence to suggest that ushnus were places in which offerings could be made to the earth and other sentient landscape beings (such as mountains). These offerings were diverse in form, including libations of chicha (maize beer) and buried artifacts of gold, silver and exotic marine shell. In some cases, ritually killed humans may have been associated with ushnu platforms as well.

↳ Devotional markers:

– No

Notes: There is no evidence of any religious phenomenon in the Inca context that could be

interpreted as a devotional marker.

↳ Mass gathering point [plazas, courtyard, square. Places permanently demarcated using visible objects or structures]:

– Yes

Notes: Many major Inca settlements were organized around large open-air spaces and plazas, frequently trapezoidal in plan. One of the most obvious cases is the Awkaypata, the "terrace of repose" at the heart of the Inca capital of Cusco. Ethnohistoric evidence suggests that ceremonies involving the mummified rulers of the Inca Empire often took place in the Awkaypata. Many other Inca settlements in the provinces, such as Huánuco Pampa in the Huánuco region of Peru, were centered on massive plazas too. At the center of many of these formally demarcated spaces were the ceremonial platforms called ushnus and it is clear that mass gatherings of a ritual nature frequently took place there, accommodating hundreds of even thousands of individuals at a time. Archaeological evidence (especially in the form of ceramic vessels) indicates that state-sponsored feasts were a significant component of the ceremonial events associated with Inca plazas.

↳ Other type of religious monumental architecture:

– Yes [specify]: Acclahuasi

Notes: The acclahuasi were houses for the "chosen women" of the empire, where a number of adolescent females were sent for instruction in religious ritual and crafting (especially the making of maize beer and weaving). The women who ran the acclahuasi were expected to remain virgins throughout their lives and many Spanish observers therefore likened them to "convents". Some acclahuasi were impressively monumental structures, capable of housing hundreds of women and girls. Archaeologically-known examples have been identified at Pachacamac on the Pacific coasts near modern Lima and at Huánuco Pampa in the central highlands of Peru.

Is iconography present:

– Yes

Notes: Inca visual culture was mostly geometric and abstract, with relatively few instances of figurative imagery present. However, there are some contexts in which figurative representation does consistently occur. These include high-altitude complexes in which offerings were made to deified mountains, which often have figurines made of gold or silver, in the shape of humans or camelids (i.e. llamas and alpacas). Small stone artifacts called conopas were also produced by the Incas, which are always in the shape of camelids. These objects typically had small basins or reservoirs for holding ritually charged substances, especially animal fat. Some Inca ceramics include painted or molded representations of animals, such as insects, birds and felines.

↳ Where is iconography present [select all that apply]:

– Some public spaces

↳ Are there distinct features in the religious group's iconography:

– Yes

↳ Eyes (stylized or not):

– Yes

Notes: Inca anthropomorphic and zoomorphic figurines always include eyes (shown open). Outside of this context, however, the depiction of eyes is very rare.

↳ Supernatural beings (zoomorphic):

– No

Notes: Although zoomorphic beings are sometimes depicted in Inca art (mostly llamas, alpacas, waterfowl, insects and felines), there are no explicitly supernatural elements in this iconography.

↳ Supernatural beings (geomorphic):

– No

Notes: Nothing resembling a supernatural geomorphic being can be identified in Inca visual culture.

↳ Supernatural beings (anthropomorphic):

– No

Notes: Although anthropomorphic beings are sometimes depicted in Inca art, there are no explicitly supernatural elements in this iconography.

↳ Supernatural beings (abstract symbol):

– No

Notes: The meanings of Inca abstract motifs and symbols are not always well understood. Some clearly depict stylized vegetal forms (like maize plants), however, there is no evidence to suggest that any such symbols were understood as supernatural beings.

↳ Portrayals of afterlife:

– No

Notes: Narrative scenes in general (whether depicting the afterlife or anything else) are absent from Inca art.

↳ Aspects of doctrine (e.g. cross, trinity, Mithraic symbols):

– Yes

Notes: Some recurring symbols in Inca visual culture likely had some sort of cosmological meaning, even if the details are not fully understood today. The most obvious example is the so-called chakana; a stepped cross motif that was found in a variety of ancient Andean contexts. The most famous Inca instance of a chakana is a cruciform relief carving on the surface of a monolith within the Inca royal estate of Ollantaytambo. It is worth noting, however, that the chakana is much more common among pre-Inca cultures as compared to the Incas themselves.

↳ Humans:

– Yes

Notes: Human images in the Inca case almost always take the form of figurines of gold or silver that were included in ritual offerings. Beyond this special case, there was very little anthropomorphic iconography in the Inca Empire.

↳ Other features of iconography:

– Yes

Notes: Carved bedrock outcrops were one of the most common types of shrine in the Inca Empire. However, the carvings seldom include figurative elements of any kind, instead mostly consisting of steps, platforms, channels and other geometric shapes. There are only a few cases of figuratively carved stones in the Inca Empire. One example is the Saywite Stone, a freestanding monolith decorated with over 200 relief carvings of humans, animals and landscape features (e.g. agricultural terraces). This carved stone was clearly an Inca shrine as well, but its dense figurative carving was virtually unique.

Beliefs

Burial and Afterlife

Is a spirit-body distinction present:

Answer “no” only if personhood (or consciousness) is extinguished with death of the physical body. Answering yes does not necessarily imply the existence of Cartesian mind/body dualism, merely that some element of personhood (or consciousness) survives the death of the body.

– No

Notes: The Inca (as with many Indigenous American societies) drew no distinction between body and spirit. After the Inca Empire was conquered by the Spanish, words like "spirit" and "soul" were especially difficult for the Catholic missionaries to translate into local languages, who often relied on Spanish loanwords to convey such concepts.

Belief in afterlife:

– Yes

↳ Is the spatial location of the afterlife specified or described by the religious group:

– Yes

Notes: The afterlife involves a change of state, in which deceased humans become ancestors (especially via mummification). But this is not understood as another place or different plane of existence. There is no body-spirit distinction in Inca cosmology, so ancestorhood is an entirely physical condition, and there are therefore no beliefs about immaterial souls leaving the body to reside in another kind of reality.

Reincarnation in this world:

– No

Notes: Reincarnation was not a feature of Inca belief

Are there special treatments for adherents' corpses:

– Yes

Notes: Archaeological evidence indicates that cremation never occurred among the Incas. According to ethnohistoric accounts, the Inca emperor Atahualpa (following his capture by the Spanish in 1532) was afraid they would kill him and then burn his corpse, resulting in his permanent physical destruction. The implication is that the dead should retain their physical integrity in order to persist as a person in the afterlife. For similar reasons, there seems to be no evidence of exposure of the dead (to wild animals or the elements). Instead, subterranean burial was the dominant form of treatment of the dead in Inca culture. For the most part, the deceased were interred in clay capsules or pits. Some dead individuals, usually those of higher status, were mummified and continued to play an active role in human affairs. Such mummies (mainly of dead royalty) constantly moved from place to place, taking part in feasts, political ceremonies and other social events. Mummification was the best means available to the Incas for the long-term preservation of the physical body, further underscoring how important this principle was to them.

↳ Cremation:

– No

Notes: Cremation never took place among the Incas.

↳ Mummification:

– Yes

Notes: Mummification often occurred among the Incas, but seems to have been mainly reserved for high-status individuals. The process was carried out by naturally freeze-drying the corpse (something easily done in the high-altitude Andean mountains).

↳ Interment:

– Yes

Notes: Interment was the norm for lower-status individuals in the Inca Empire.

↳ Cannibalism:

– No

Notes: There is no evidence for cannibalism among the Incas. Ethnohistoric reports from the colonial period indicate that the Incas were aware of the practice of cannibalism among Indigenous Amazonian peoples, and furthermore, that the Incas considered such practices to be uncivilized.

↳ Exposure to elements (e.g. air drying):

– No

Notes: Exposure of corpses to the elements was not practiced by the Incas. They did mummify individuals by freeze-drying them at high altitude, however, this occurred indoors in well-

ventilated structures designed specifically for this purpose.

↳ Feeding to animals:

– No

Notes: The Incas did not generally expose the already-dead to animals. Occasionally, still-living prisoners were thrown into a pit with anacondas, pumas and jaguars as a form of punishment.

↳ Secondary burial:

– Yes

Notes: Most corpses were not disturbed after burial, but in some instances they were moved or relocated after death. Royal mummies were exceptionally itinerant, constantly participating in social events and affairs of state.

↳ Re-treatment of corpse:

– No

Notes: There is little evidence of re-treatments of corpses after the initial preparation and burial.

↳ Other intensive (in terms of time or resources expended) treatment of corpse :

– No

Are co-sacrifices present in tomb/burial:

– Field doesn't know

Notes: There is no direct archaeological evidence of co-sacrifices in Inca burials. Various ethnohistoric accounts suggest that Inca rulers might have been interred with their wives and other co-sacrifices, particularly women, although this lacks archaeological corroboration.

Are grave goods present:

– Yes

↳ Personal effects:

– Yes

Notes: Some of the items (e.g. ceramics, jewelry) found within Inca burials were very likely personal effects.

↳ Valuable items:

– Yes

↳ Significant wealth (e.g. gold, jade, intensely worked objects):

– Yes

Notes: Precious metals (in the form of jewelry like clothing pins) are found in Inca burials. But the most important form of high-value grave good was textiles. The dead were often wrapped in many layers of finely woven cloth, considered one of the most valuable substances in the Inca Empire. Of particular import were fine wools obtained from camelids like the alpaca and vicuña.

↳ Some wealth (some valuable or useful objects interred):

– Yes

Notes: Ceramic vessels were a common grave good in Inca contexts, especially serving vessels in the imperial style (i.e. painted and burnished polychrome pottery).

↳ Other valuable/precious items interred:

– No

↳ Other grave goods:

– No

Are formal burials present:

– Yes

↳ As cenotaphs:

– No

↳ In cemetery:

– Yes

Notes: Inca cemeteries exist, although they do not always have any aboveground or architectural markers for graves. Some cemeteries were placed into the side of cliffs.

↳ Family tomb-crypt:

– Yes

Notes: Burials often include a number of closely related individuals.

↳ Domestic (individuals interred beneath house, or in areas used for normal domestic activities):

– Yes

Notes: Burials of infants often occur beneath domestic spaces or in architectural contexts.

↳ Other formal burial type:

– No

Supernatural Beings

Are supernatural beings present:

– Yes

↳ A supreme high god is present:

– No

Notes: The Inca creator deity Wiracocha is often interpreted in colonial sources as equivalent to a supreme high god (similar to the Christian God) although this is probably a partially Christianized understanding of Inca cosmology. It is unclear if the pre-colonial understanding of Wiracocha fully conforms to this view. Along with Wiracocha, the deified sun (Inti) was the most important divine being in the imperial pantheon. Of lower rank, but still highly significant were deities like Mamaquilla (mother-moon) and Inti-Llapa (Thunder).

↳ Previously human spirits are present:

– No

Notes: The mummified bodies of some ancestors (especially royalty) were venerated in the Inca Empire, a common feature of pre-colonial Andean religion in general. These mummies could speak, eat and engage with the living in a variety of social contexts. They were also regarded as full members of society, continuing to own property and exercise political rights. As ancestors, they also had the power to influence the fertility of their descendants. However, there was no body-spirit distinction in Inca cosmology, and mummies were thus entirely physical beings, governed by the same fundamental material restrictions as living humans. They were subject to damage or destruction, just like living bodies, and they could not pass through physical objects. There is no evidence that the incorporeal spirits of the dead were thought to persist or interact with humans in the Inca context.

↳ Non-human supernatural beings are present:

– Yes

↳ These supernatural beings can be seen:

– Yes

Notes: Supernatural beings were usually in the form of landscape features (especially rocks, mountains and bodies of water). They are fully present in the physical realm and thus visible.

↳ These supernatural beings can be physically felt:

– Yes

Notes: Supernatural beings were usually in the form of landscape features (especially rocks, mountains and bodies of water). They are fully present in the physical realm and thus entirely capable of tactile interaction.

↳ Non-human supernatural beings have knowledge of this world:

– Yes

↳ Non-human supernatural beings have knowledge restricted to particular domain of human affairs:

– No

Notes: There is no specialization in the knowledge supernatural beings have of human affairs.

↳ Non-human supernatural beings have knowledge restricted to (a) specific area(s) within the sample region:

– Field doesn't know

Notes: Information on the precise range of knowledge possessed by Inca supernatural beings is limited.

↳ Non-human supernatural beings have knowledge unrestricted within the sample region:

– Field doesn't know

Notes: Information on the precise range of knowledge possessed by Inca supernatural beings is limited.

↳ Non-human supernatural beings have knowledge unrestricted outside of sample region:

– Field doesn't know

Notes: Information on the precise range of knowledge possessed by Inca supernatural beings is limited.

↳ Non-human supernatural beings can see you everywhere normally visible (in public):

– Yes

Notes: Supernatural beings have similar powers of visibility to humans. They can therefore see things that occur in public spaces.

↳ Non-human supernatural beings can see you everywhere (in the dark, at home):

– Field doesn't know

Notes: Information on the precise range of knowledge possessed by Inca supernatural beings is limited. It is unclear what limitations might have existed on their powers of perception, or if anything could be concealed from them.

↳ Non-human supernatural beings can see inside heart/mind (hidden

motives):

– Field doesn't know

Notes: Information on the precise range of knowledge possessed by Inca supernatural beings is limited. There is no information as to whether or not they could perceive unspoken thoughts or desires.

↳ Non-human supernatural beings knows your basic character (personal essence):

– Field doesn't know

Notes: Information on the precise range of knowledge possessed by Inca supernatural beings is limited. There is no information as to whether they could know the basic character of humans.

↳ Non-human supernatural beings know what will happen to you, what you will do (future sight):

– Yes

Notes: Certain non-human supernatural beings in the Inca Empire had oracular powers and could foretell future events. A famous example was the rock outcrop of Catequil, which was well-known for its skills in divination. It is unclear if all supernatural beings had such abilities, or only some. It is also unclear if they had absolute or perfect knowledge of the future, or whether it was only partial.

↳ Non-human supernatural beings have other knowledge of this world:

– Field doesn't know

Notes: Information on the precise range of knowledge possessed by Inca supernatural beings is limited.

↳ Non-human supernatural beings have deliberate causal efficacy in the world:

– Yes

↳ These supernatural beings can reward:

– Yes

Notes: Many non-human supernatural beings have power over the weather (especially deified mountains) and can positively impact humans by ensuring meteorological conditions are favorable. Rock outcrops are often understood as the owners of the agricultural fields and can influence the fertility and abundance of the crops grown in such locations.

↳ These supernatural beings can punish:

– Yes

Notes: Many non-human supernatural beings have power over the weather

(especially deified mountains) and can negatively impact humans by sending storms, floods, lightning and so on. Rock outcrops are often understood as the owners of the agricultural fields and if not appropriately treated (with offerings of gifts and libations), can harm the crops grown in such locations.

↳ These supernatural beings have indirect causal efficacy in the world:

– No

Notes: Supernatural beings deliberately and consciously bring about effects in the world.

↳ These supernatural beings exhibit positive emotion:

– Yes

Notes: As far as is known, supernatural beings in the Inca context exhibit similar emotional states to humans.

↳ These supernatural beings exhibit negative emotion:

– Yes

Notes: As far as is known, supernatural beings in the Inca context exhibit similar emotional states to humans.

↳ These supernatural beings possess hunger:

– Yes

Notes: Supernatural beings in the Inca context are fully physical, and thus require continuous nourishment in the form of offerings.

↳ These supernatural beings possess/exhibit some other feature:

– Yes [specify]: Mortality

Notes: At least some supernatural beings were mortal; subject to being wounded or killed. When the rock outcrop Catequil predicted the future defeat of the Inca emperor Atahualpa, he ordered its execution for treason. Subsequently, the outcrop and the hilltop upon which it resided were destroyed by the imperial armies, neutralizing the supernatural being in question.

↳ Does the religious group possess a variety of supernatural beings:

– Yes

Notes: Supernatural beings in the Inca world included celestial entities (e.g. the sun, the moon, thunder) and well terrestrial entities (e.g. mountains, the sea, lakes, springs, rocks).

↳ Organized by kinship based on a family model:

– Yes

Notes: Virtually all relationships in the Inca Empire were understood as kin

relationships. Supernatural beings related to each other as kin, while relationships between supernatural beings and living humans were also kin-based. For example, the deified sun was the father of the Inca rulers. The deified moon was the wife of the sun. In ethnohistoric accounts, the Incas routinely referred to sentient rock outcrops (huacas) as their brothers, or male ancestors. The deified earth (Pachamama) was understood as a maternal being with respect to all terrestrial creatures.

↳ Organized hierarchically:

– Yes

Notes: Because all relationships in Inca cosmology are kin relations, this inherently entails hierarchy. The deified sun (Inti) is the spouse of the deified moon (Mamaquilla) and thus deemed superior to her. The deified sun is the father of the Inca emperors, and is thus deemed superior to his human children. Ancestral beings in general (which can be rock outcrops or mummified humans) are accorded respect and veneration by all their descendants.

↳ Power of beings is domain specific:

– No

Notes: Whereas deities in other religious traditions often have specific areas of power (e.g. war, death and the afterlife, healing) this was not a feature of the Inca pantheon. The powers of Inca supernaturals primarily differed in degree, rather than kind. For instance, a large mountain might exert power of a more extensive geographical area than a smaller rock outcrop. Similarly, an ancestral being mainly exerts power over their own descendants.

↳ Other organization for pantheon:

– No

Supernatural Monitoring

Is supernatural monitoring present:

This refers to surveillance by supernatural beings of humans' behaviour and/or thought particularly as it relates to social norms or potential norm violations.

– No

Notes: Evidence suggest that supernatural beings in the Inca context were deeply concerned about their social relationships with humans. They wished to ensure they would continue to receive offerings from humans in particular. However, there is no evidence that supernatural beings observed or monitored human activity for its own sake, or were interested in enforcing any particular set of ethical norms with respect to behavior between humans.

Do supernatural beings mete out punishment:

– Yes

↳ Is the cause or agent of supernatural punishment known:

– Yes

↳ Done only by high god:

– No

Notes: There is no high god in Inca cosmology

↳ Done by many supernatural beings:

– Yes

Notes: Punishments are meted out in response to failure to maintain appropriate relationships with a supernatural being (e.g. lack of offerings). The punishment would be meted out by the supernatural being who had been slighted.

↳ Done through impersonal cause-effect principle:

– No

Notes: Punishments are meted out in response to failure to maintain appropriate relationships with a supernatural being (e.g. lack of offerings). The punishment would be meted out directly by the supernatural being who had been slighted.

↳ Done by other entities or through other means [specify]

– No

Notes: Punishments are meted out in response to failure to maintain appropriate relationships with a supernatural being (e.g. lack of offerings). The punishment would be meted out by the supernatural being who had been slighted.

↳ Is the reason for supernatural punishment known:

– Yes

Notes: Punishments are meted out in response to a human failure to maintain appropriate relationships with a supernatural being (e.g. lack of offerings).

↳ Done to enforce religious ritual-devotional adherence:

– No

Notes: Punishments are meted out in response to a human failure to maintain appropriate relationships with a supernatural being (e.g. lack of offerings). Punishments are not directed at humans independently of their personal relationships to supernatural beings.

↳ Done to enforce group norms:

– No

Notes: Supernatural beings are generally unconcerned with the group norms of

humans.

↳ Done to inhibit selfishness:

– No

Notes: Supernatural beings are generally unconcerned with enforcing human ethical norms.

↳ Done randomly:

– No

Notes: Punishments are meted out in response to failure to maintain appropriate relationships with a supernatural being (e.g. lack of offerings). Supernatural beings generally do not seek to harm humans for no reason or at random.

↳ Other [specify]

– No

Notes: There are no other common reasons for supernatural punishment.

↳ Supernatural punishments are meted out in the afterlife:

– Field doesn't know

Notes: Although ethnographic accounts of modern Indigenous peoples in the Andes include a belief in punishments in the afterlife, it is unknown if the Incas (over 500 years earlier) had any specific ideas about post-mortem acts of punishment.

↳ Supernatural punishments are meted out in this lifetime:

– Yes

↳ Supernatural punishments in this life are highly emphasized by the religious group:

– Yes

Notes: The negative consequences of not properly maintaining good relationships with supernatural beings was a core feature of Inca State religion.

↳ Punishment in this life consists of bad luck:

– No

Notes: Punishments are not random, but specific and targeted and the human (or community) that caused the offense.

↳ Punishment in this life consists of political failure:

– No

↳ Punishment in this life consists of defeat in battle:

– No

↳ Punishment in this life consists of crop failure or bad weather:

– Yes

Notes: The primary means of punishment available to supernaturals in the Inca world was their ability to negatively impact the productivity and fertility of the land, often by causing crop failures or sending bad weather.

↳ Punishment in this life consists of disaster on journeys.

– No

↳ Punishment in this life consists of mild sensory displeasure:

– No

↳ Punishment in this life consists of extreme sensory displeasure:

– No

↳ Punishment in this life consists of sickness or illness:

– Yes

Notes: Since supernatural beings control fertility and reproduction, one way in which they can negatively affect humans is to cause illness or a lack of vitality.

↳ Punishment in this life consists of impaired reproduction:

– Yes

Notes: Supernaturals generally control fertility and reproduction, so reduction of either is a core form of punishment available to them when offended by humans.

↳ Punishment in this life consists of bad luck visited on descendants:

– No

Notes: Supernatural punishments are generally specific and targeted, rather than simply a form of bad luck.

↳ Other [specify]

– No

Do supernatural beings bestow rewards:

– Yes

↳ Is the cause/purpose of supernatural rewards known:

– Yes

↳ Done only by high god:

– No

↳ Done by many supernatural beings:

– Yes

Notes: All supernatural beings have social relationships with humans and actively reward human communities (mainly with fertility and the reproduction of crops, animals and humans) if they are appropriately treated. Supernatural beings generally expect offerings from humans, and social interaction in general (i.e. feasting and dance).

↳ Done through impersonal cause-effect principle:

– No

Notes: Supernatural beings interactions with humans are highly personalized in all respects.

↳ Done to enforce religious ritual-devotional adherence:

– No

Notes: Supernatural beings interactions with humans are largely self-interested. They reward humans in exchange for offerings and social interaction; they do not reward humans for general adherence to religious or ritual practices.

↳ Done to enforce group norms:

– No

Notes: Supernatural beings are largely uninterested in group norms.

↳ Done to inhibit selfishness¹:

– No

Notes: Supernatural beings are largely uninterested in enforcing ethical behavior in humans.

↳ Done randomly:

– No

Notes: Supernatural rewards are consciously given and represent a direct return for the offerings provided by humans; they are not random.

↳ Supernatural rewards are bestowed out in the afterlife:

– Field doesn't know

Notes: There is no evidence that supernatural rewards are provided to humans when dead; all available evidence relates to rewards received during life.

↳ Supernatural rewards are bestowed out in this lifetime:

– Yes

↳ Supernatural rewards in this life are highly emphasized by the religious group:

– Yes

Notes: Rewards received from supernatural beings (especially fertility and reproductive success) were the core of Inca state religion.

↳ Reward in this life consists of good luck:

– No

Notes: Rewards provided by supernatural beings are not random; but targeted and specific—as part of the debts supernaturals accrue with respect to the humans who provide them with offerings.

↳ Reward in this life consists of political success or power:

– No

↳ Reward in this life consists of success in battle:

– Yes

Notes: In some ethnohistoric accounts, there is a story of how a group of rocks came to life and aided the Inca emperor in battle against the Chanka ethnic group in the early days of imperial expansion. However, this is not a common form of supernatural reward, which typically focus on providing fertility and reproductive success.

↳ Reward in this life consists of peace or social stability:

– No

↳ Reward in this life consists of healthy crops or good weather:

– Yes

Notes: Good weather and healthy crops are among the main forms of reward provided by supernatural beings to humans.

↳ Reward in this life consists of success on journeys:

– No

↳ Reward in this life consists of mild sensory pleasure:

– No

↳ Reward in this life consists of extreme sensory pleasure:

– No

↳ Reward in this life consists of enhanced health:

– Yes

Notes: Insofar as fertility and reproductive success can be seen as form of enhanced health, supernaturals do often reward humans in this way.

↳ Reward in this life consists of enhanced reproductive success:

– Yes

Notes: Enhanced reproductive success is one of the main ways in which supernaturals reward humans.

↳ Reward in this life consists of fortune visited on descendants:

– No

Notes: Influence on personal luck or fortune is not a common feature of how supernaturals reward humans. Rewards are conscious and targeted, rather than random.

↳ Other [specify]

– No

Messianism/Eschatology

Are messianic beliefs present:

– Field doesn't know

Notes: It is possible that messianic beliefs existed in the Inca Empire, but there is insufficient evidence to say with any confidence.

Is an eschatology present:

– Yes

Notes: Ethnohistoric accounts indicate that eschatology was a fundamental feature of Inca cosmology. Specifically, there was a belief in the cycling of different "suns" in which the world was profoundly altered and then recreated. The Incas understood themselves to be living in the age of the Fifth Sun, which according to the account of the Indigenous chronicler Blas Valera (written down in the early colonial period) had begun in 1043 CE. Another fundamental concept in Inca eschatology was "pachakuti", a Quechua word that refers to a "turning over of time and space". These cataclysmic events

brought about the transformation and recreation of the world. The Inca noble Inca Yupanqui is often credited in surviving ethnohistoric sources as having founded the Inca Empire, after which he took on the epithet Pachakuti to indicate that his ascent to power had transformed the world.

↳ Eschaton in this lifetime:

– No

Notes: Cycling between worlds (called Ages of the Sun) is a general feature of Inca cosmology. But there is no expectation that this will occur in one's own lifetime, and generally many centuries pass between each new cycle.

↳ Eschaton at specified time in future:

– Field doesn't know

Notes: According to some ethnohistoric accounts, each age of the sun was expected to last for a thousand years. Whether this was meant literally, or just to indicate "a very long time" is unclear.

↳ Eschaton at unspecified time in near future:

– Field doesn't know

Notes: The general cycling between different Ages of the Sun was a core feature of Inca cosmology, but it does not seem that the timing of future cycles was very precisely predicted. Some accounts do suggest that each Age of the Sun would last for around a thousand years.

↳ Eschaton at unspecified time in distant future:

– Field doesn't know

Notes: The general cycling between different Ages of the Sun was a core feature of Inca cosmology, but it does not seem that the timing of future cycles was very precisely predicted. Some accounts do suggest that each Age of the Sun would last for around a thousand years.

↳ Eschaton at some other time:

– No

↳ Adherents need to perform specific tasks to bring about World's end:

– No

Notes: There is no evidence that the Incas understood the end of the world to be dependent on specific human actions.

↳ Divine judgment event:

– No

Notes: There is no evidence that divine judgment (or divine agency in general) were significant features of Inca eschatology.

↳ Restoration of the world:

– Yes

Notes: Each new "Age of the Sun" implies the regeneration of the world in an altered form.

↳ Start of a new temporal cycle:

– Yes

Notes: A new "Age of the Sun" is begun with each fulfillment of an eschatological cycle. The Incas understood themselves to be living within and to have helped precipitate the Fifth Sun.

↳ Establishment of a new political system:

– Yes

Notes: In several ethnohistoric accounts, the Inca Empire was associated with the establishment of the Fifth Age of the Sun, which replaced an earlier period (the Fourth Sun) associated with anarchy and disorder. Eschatological cycling and political change are therefore closely linked in Inca cosmology.

↳ Establishment of a new religious system:

– Yes

Notes: According to some ethnohistoric accounts, with the establishment of the Fifth Sun (and the Inca's rise to power) new religious practices were instituted. In particular, the focus on the deified sun (Inti) is presented as a specifically Inca innovation.

↳ Will anyone survive the eschaton:

– Yes

Notes: Periodic cycles of world renewal do not seem to entail the destruction of all humans.

Norms and Moral Realism

Are general social norms prescribed by the religious group:

– Yes

Notes: Social norms were certainly prescribed in Inca society. The most important social principle was reciprocity, which required humans and supernaturals to repay their debts to each other. Humans paid taxes (in the form of labor) to the state, while the state responded by sponsoring feasts which were enjoyed by the general population. Similarly, supernaturals received offerings of food, drink and sometimes human sacrifices, for which they were obligated to provide humans with fertility and vitality. However, the social norms of the Inca State religion were identical with those of Inca society, and indeed, Indigenous Andean cultures in general. Inca religion had no distinct social norms associated with it.

Is there a conventional vs. moral distinction in the religious group:

– Field doesn't know

Notes: Detailed knowledge or Inca moral norms is unavailable due to lack of appropriate evidence.

Practices

Membership Costs and Practices

Does membership in this religious group require celibacy (full sexual abstinence):

– Yes

Notes: Full celibacy was expected of the adult women who ran the *acllawasi*, the houses of the chosen women. These institutions trained adolescent girls in religious duties and crafting. Outside of this specific context, however, there is no evidence of full sexual abstinence in any other Inca context.

Does membership in this religious group require constraints on sexual activity (partial sexual abstinence):

– Yes

↳ Monogamy (males):

– No

Notes: Inca aristocrats had multiple wives, although only one was nominated as the principal wife. Outside of the elites, monogamy was the norm for men.

↳ Monogamy (females):

– Yes

Notes: Women, regardless of social rank, were expected to have only one husband (and sexual partner).

↳ Other sexual constraints (males):

– Yes

Notes: There were no permanently celibate male ritual specialists. However, before engaging in certain ritual activities or prior to entering some temples, male officials were expected to abstain from sex for periods of days or months to ensure their purity.

↳ Other sexual constraints (females):

– Yes

Notes: Multiple ethnohistoric sources indicate that the *mamaconas* (or *mamakuna*), a specialized group of female ritual specialist and craftworkers were celibate throughout their lives.

Does membership in this religious group require castration:

– No

Notes: There is no evidence that castration was widely practiced in the Inca Empire.

Does membership in this religious group require fasting:

– Yes

Notes: In general, dietary restrictions were observed for short periods of time prior to engaging in ritual activities among the Incas. However, Inca fasting did not entail non-consumption of food; instead it involved the avoidance of salt and pepper. Fasting therefore meant eating bland or unseasoned food in the Inca context.

Does membership in this religious group require forgone food opportunities (taboos on desired foods):

– No

Notes: There is no evidence that the Incas required or enforced food taboos with respect to the state religion.

Does membership in this religious group require permanent scarring or painful bodily alterations:

– No

Notes: There is no evidence that scarification or painful body alterations were required by the Incas. Elite individuals typically wore metal ear ornaments that elongated their earlobes over time, although this was not especially painful. As with many other ancient Andean peoples, sometimes the Incas practiced skull modification in infants (through binding), although it is unclear if this was always experienced as painful. In any event, it was far from a universal practice in the Inca Empire, nor a requirement to participate in any religious activities.

Does membership in this religious group require painful physical positions or transitory painful wounds:

– No

Notes: There is no evidence that the Inca religion required deliberate experiences of pain or wounding for ritual purposes.

Does membership in this religious group require sacrifice of adults:

"Adults" here referring to an emic or indigenous category; if that category is different from the popular Western definition of a human who is 18-years-old or older and who is legally responsible for his/her actions, then please specify that difference in the Comments/Sources: box below.

– No

Notes: There is some archaeological evidence for adults having been occasionally sacrificed by the Incas, but these instances are relatively rare and so probably did not reflect a common or institutionalized practice. Spanish missionaries writing in the colonial period often claimed that human sacrifice was practiced by the Incas on a large scale, sometimes numbering thousands of individuals at a time. Such accounts should be regarded with skepticism in the absence of archaeological corroboration, since these were standard rhetorical statements used by Christian missionaries to delegitimize Indigenous religions throughout the Americas.

Does membership in this religious group require sacrifice of children:

"Children" here referring to an emic or indigenous category; if that category is different from the popular Western definition, please specify that different in the Comments/Sources: box below.

– Yes

Notes: The sacrifice of children was a regular and institutionalized feature of the Inca state religion. The Quechua term for this form of sacrifice was Capacocha, and it was centrally organized and administered by the state. Both ethnohistoric and archaeological lines of evidence provide a fairly consistent picture of this practice and its basic contours. The preferred subjects of these sacrificial events were young boys and girls, usually between the ages of 3 and 10. The main recipient of the sacrifices were the highest rank of deities, especially Inti (the sun) and Wiracocha (the Creator). Sacrifices were obtained from across the empire, as a form of tribute, and seem to have been carried out for a variety of reasons, including in response to environmental crises or in association with the coronations of new rulers. The most abundant archaeological evidence for Capacocha rituals is found at high-altitude sites in what are now Argentina and Chile, indicating that glaciated mountains may also have been the recipients of many such offerings. However, preservation is unusually good in these locales, due to the cold and arid conditions, so their high frequency may reflect a preservation bias. A great deal of Capacocha sacrifices probably occurred at lower-elevation sites in what is now Peru, but have not survived for archaeological examination. Ethnohistoric accounts and the archaeological evidence agree that there was a preference for "unblemished" children as sacrifices, and that they were interred with offerings of gold, silver, ceramics, textiles and feathers. The most common method of killing was probably strangulation.

Does membership in this religious group require self-sacrifice (suicide):

– No

Notes: Evidence of self-sacrifice is limited in the Inca Empire.

Does membership in this religious group require sacrifice of property/valuable items:

– Yes

Notes: Offerings to supernatural beings were varied, and included items made of gold and silver, exotic marine shells, exotic feathers, high-quality textiles and ceramic vessels. The best-preserved evidence for such practices comes from high-altitude sites in the southern Andes (modern Argentina and Chile) where these items seem to have been placed on glaciated peaks as gifts to the deified mountains.

Does membership in this religious group require sacrifice of time (e.g., attendance at meetings or services, regular prayer, etc.):

– Yes

Notes: Ritual activities that entailed socializing between humans and non-human supernaturals were a fundamental feature of Inca religion. This often took the form of feasts where humans would offer food and drink to supernaturals. In addition, there are records of songs or hymns that were addressed to supernatural beings at these events.

Does membership in this religious group require physical risk taking:

– No

Notes: There is no evidence for risk-taking activities that were required or encouraged by the Inca state

religion.

Does membership in this religious group require accepting ethical precepts:

– No

Notes: The Inca state religion was focused primarily on ritual obligations and submission to the Inca ruling class. It lacked formal ethical teachings and so did not seek to inculcate such in adherents.

Does membership in this religious group require marginalization by out-group members:

– No

Notes: The Inca Empire was an expansive polity that sought to encompass the entirety of the known world, and by extension, all its peoples. As such, there was no marginalization of out-group members. Incorporation into the activities of the state religion was hierarchical (some were expected to do more than others, especially if they were elites and resided near the capital), but no-one was fully excluded.

Does membership in this religious group require participation in small-scale rituals (private, household):

– No

Notes: Inca state religion was largely unconcerned with non-public religious practices occurring within households. Of course, religious practices associated with individual kin groups would have been much more concerned with domestic-level rituals.

Does membership in this religious group require participation in large-scale rituals:

I.e. involving two or more households; includes large-scale “ceremonies” and “festivals.”

– Yes

On average, for large-scale rituals how many participants gather in one location:

– Field doesn't know

Notes: It is difficult to provide precise estimates for large-scale ritual gatherings in Inca contexts. The largest plazas in the empire were clearly designed to accommodate thousands of people at a time; although it's very difficult to say if those numbers regularly assembled from archaeological evidence alone. In addition, many smaller-scale public rituals probably occurred with a only few hundred participants.

What is the average interval of time between performances (in hours):

Performances here refers to large-scale rituals.

– Field doesn't know

Notes: We know that major rituals gatherings were associated with the solstices, although we have no precise information to determine how often ritual gatherings occurred in general.

Are there orthodoxy checks:

Orthodoxy checks are mechanisms used to ensure that rituals are interpreted in a standardized way, e.g. through the supervisory prominence of a professionalized priesthood or other system of governance, appeal to texts detailing the proper interpretation, etc.

– No

Notes: Inca religion had no formal doctrines.

↳ Are there orthopraxy checks:

Orthopraxy checks are mechanisms used to ensure that rituals are performed in a standardized way, e.g. through the supervisory prominence of a professionalized priesthood or other system of governance, appeal to texts detailing the proper procedure, etc.

– Yes

Notes: State officials would have ensured that ritual activities accorded with the traditional norms. Archaeological evidence shows that certain rituals (e.g. sacrifice of children) were highly standardized in state contexts, and so must have been regulated by Inca authorities to some degree.

↳ Does participation entail synchronic practices:

– Field doesn't know

Notes: Details of the practices entailed in large ritual gatherings are not known from current evidence.

↳ Is there use of intoxicants:

– Yes

Notes: The drinking of beer (fermented maize) was a central element of virtually all state ritual in Inca contexts. In particular, the ceremonies associated with the winter (Qhapaq Raymi) and summer (Inti Raymi) solstices entailed large-scale feasting and drinking of alcohol. Libations of alcohol were also regularly provided for supernatural beings, especially sentient features of the landscape (often called huacas). This is well-attested for rock outcrops, where archaeological studies have furnished evidence of ceramic vessels used to provide these non-human supernaturals with food and drink. Conversely, there is very limited evidence for hallucinogen consumption in the Inca Empire, and it seems it was not a major component of state ritual.

Are extra-ritual in-group markers present:

E.g. special changes to appearance such as circumcision, tattoos, scarification, etc.

– No

Notes: Group markers in the Inca context were primarily ethnic (e.g. certain textile styles) or class-based (elongated ears from wearing metal ornaments). There were no religious group markers.

Does the group employ fictive kinship terminology:

– No

Notes: Kinship terminology was always used for nonhuman supernaturals. For example, the sun was a father to the Inca rulers, whereas living shrines (huacas) were often described as the brothers of the

Incas. However, the use of fictive kin terminology between humans who participated in the Inca state religion is not attested.

Society and Institutions

Levels of Social Complexity

The society to which the religious group belongs is best characterized as (please choose one):

– An empire

Notes: The Inca Empire was the largest state to emerge in the pre-colonial Americas. It was an urban society, characterized by centralized government and with a powerful ruling class. Overall, the imperial population probably numbered around 12 million inhabitants.

Welfare

Does the religious group in question provide institutionalized famine relief:

– Field doesn't know

Notes: There is no evidence of how the Inca State or its religious institutions responded to famine events.

Is famine relief available to the group's adherents through an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– Field doesn't know

Notes: There is insufficient evidence available to assess how famine events were dealt with in the context of the Inca Empire.

Does the religious group in question provide institutionalized poverty relief:

– No

Notes: The economy of the Inca Empire was non-capitalist with very little, if any, market exchange. Property (mainly agricultural land) was not owned by individuals or nuclear families, but by larger kin groups (called ayllus) which typically numbered in the hundreds or thousands of people. Most redistribution of resources to alleviate shortages would have occurred within the framework of these kin groups.

Is poverty relief available to the group's adherents through an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– Yes

Notes: If any individual or group in the Inca Empire were to suffer a lack of resources (e.g. from localized crop failures), they would have relied on their wider kin group (called an ayllu) to redistribute food in their support. All property was held in common by kin groups, rather than individuals or nuclear families.

Does the religious group in question provide institutionalized care for the elderly and infirm:

– No

Notes: There is no evidence of the state religion of the Inca Empire specifically providing for the care of the elderly or infirm, which would have generally been the responsibility of individual kin groups.

Is institutionalized care for the elderly and infirm available to the group's adherents through an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– Yes

Notes: Andean kin groups (called ayllus) would have been the primary institution that provided care for the elderly and infirm.

Education

Does the religious group provide formal education to its adherents:

– Yes

Notes: For commoners, there was no formal education as such, and they would have been taught important skills and knowledge by more senior members of their kin groups. For elite individuals, more formal educational arrangements existed. The male children of local elites were required to reside in the capital of Cusco, where they were educated by a class of intellectuals called amautas. The subjects of their instruction would have included the ritual practices of the state religion, among other things. Adolescent girls called acllacuna (chosen women) were educated in state institutions called acllawasi, where they were taught a mixture of ritual observances and crafting skills. Some of the acllacuna became priestesses called mamacuna upon completing their education.

Is formal education available to the group's adherents through an institution(s) other than the religious group:

– Yes

Notes: The education of elite males, although covering matters of ritual and religion, were organized through the state—in the sense that they were educated at the royal court and by court intellectuals (i.e. the amauta). By contrast, the chosen women (acllacuna) who were taught in the houses of the chosen women (acllahuasi) could be seen as being directly educated through an institutional arm of the state religion.

Bureaucracy

Do the group's adherents interact with a formal bureaucracy within their group:

– Yes

Notes: The Inca State, within which the state religion was embedded, was highly bureaucratic. Within the Inca Empire, extensive records were kept of taxes (paid in the form of labor service) and of the diverse goods held in state storage facilities. There were also frequent censuses. A significant portion of the imperial bureaucracy was given over the management of resources controlled by Inca religious institutions. In particular, in multiple ethnohistoric accounts it is claimed that around a third of the land in the empire was apportioned for maintaining the cult of the deified sun.

Do the group's adherents interact with other institutional bureaucracies:

– No

Notes: The Inca religion was fully integrated into the Inca State. There was no other bureaucracy other than that of the state itself.

Public Works

Does the religious group in question provide public food storage:

– No

Notes: The Inca State stored large quantities of food, mainly used to sustain workers or soldiers engaged in projects directed by the government. However, there was no distinct provision of public food storage by state religious institutions.

Is public food storage provided to the group's adherents by an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– Yes

Notes: The Inca State stored large quantities of food, mainly used to sustain workers or soldiers engaged in projects directed by the government.

Does the religious group in question provide water management (irrigation, flood control):

– No

Notes: Water management on a large-scale was generally organized through the state in provincial contexts, while local kin groups would have dealt with smaller-scale irrigation projects. In the capital region, water management (focused on irrigation) was managed by royal kin groups. Irrigation systems were closely integrated with shrine networks, meaning that water management had ritualized and religious aspects. However, religious institutions did not directly oversee water systems independently of kin groups or the state.

Is water management provided to the group's adherents by an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– Yes

Notes: Water management on a large-scale was generally organized through the state in provincial contexts, while local kin groups would have dealt with smaller-scale irrigation projects. In the capital region, water management (focused on irrigation) was managed by royal kin groups. Irrigation systems were closely integrated with shrine networks, meaning that water management had ritualized and religious aspects. However, religious institutions did not directly oversee water systems independently of kin groups or the state.

Does the religious group in question provide transportation infrastructure:

– No

Notes: Transportation infrastructure was not provided by the religious institutions of the Inca State.

Is transportation infrastructure provided for the group's adherents by an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– Yes

Notes: The Inca State invested substantial resources in creating highway systems across the Andes, resulting in a road network with a cumulative length of at least 70,000 kilometers. Many bridges were also built at important crossing points for rivers.

Taxation

Does the religious group in question levy taxes or tithes:

– Yes

Notes: A significant portion of taxes (always levied in labor, rather than goods) would have gone to support state religious institutions, especially the cult of the deified sun.

Are taxes levied on the group's adherents by an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– Yes

Notes: All inhabitants of the Inca Empire would have been required to pay taxes to support a wide variety of state projects, in addition to the taxes used to provision state religious institutions. These taxes would have included military service, building transport or agricultural infrastructures, working on state farms and making craft goods. In the Inca context, all taxes were paid in labor service, never as goods. Money was not used in the Inca Empire.

Enforcement

Does the religious group in question provide an institutionalized police force:

– No

Notes: There was nothing resembling a police force in the Inca State.

Do the group's adherents interact with an institutionalized police force provided by an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– No

Notes: There was nothing resembling a police force in the Inca State.

Does the religious group in question provide institutionalized judges:

– No

Notes: There were no institutionalized judges in the Inca Empire, whether religious or otherwise. Administration of punishment would have been carried out by senior members of kin groups, or by state officials as a part of their general leadership roles.

Do the group's adherents interact with an institutionalized judicial system provided by an an

institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– No

Notes: There were no institutionalized judges in the Inca Empire, whether religious or otherwise.

Does the religious group in question enforce institutionalized punishment:

– No

Notes: Ethnohistoric accounts suggest that certain punishments were occasionally meted out by the Inca State. For example, some individuals were thrown into a pit called a zancay, where wild animals like jaguars, pumas and anacondas were kept. Leaders of rebellions were also commonly executed by decapitation. However, there is no evidence for specifically religious forms of institutionalized punishment.

Are the group's adherents subject to institutionalized punishment enforced by an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– Yes

Do the institutionalized punishments include execution:

– Yes

Notes: Capital punishment was practiced by the Inca State.

Do the institutionalized punishments include exile:

– No

Notes: Although groups were often forcibly relocated from their homelands as a form of punishment, complete exile from the empire did not occur.

Do the institutionalized punishments include corporal punishments:

– Yes

Notes: Corporal punishments would have been carried out by state officials or the heads of local kin groups in the normal performance of their leadership roles.

Do the institutionalized punishments include ostracism:

– Field doesn't know

Notes: There is no evidence for ostracism in the Inca Empire, although it may have occurred.

Do the institutionalized punishments include seizure of property:

– Yes

Notes: Property in the Inca Empire was held in common by kin groups, rather than individuals or nuclear families. However, the state or royal lineages did frequently seize property (in the form of land) from subject populations.

Does the religious group in question have a formal legal code:

– No

Notes: As far as is known, the Inca Empire lacked formal legal codes, religious or otherwise.

Are the group's adherents subject to a formal legal code provided by institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– No

Notes: As far as is known, the Inca Empire lacked formal legal codes, religious or otherwise.

Warfare

Does religious group in question possess an institutionalized military:

– No

Notes: The Inca State itself constantly conscripted individuals to fight wars; as a form of labor tax. However, the institutions of the state religion had no independent powers of conscription.

Do the group's adherents participate in an institutionalized military provided by institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– Yes

Notes: As an expansive empire, the Inca State had a large military apparatus that encompassed large swathes of the commoner and the aristocratic classes. Most participants in the state religion would therefore have also participated in the empire's wars to some degree.

Are the group's adherents protected by or subject to an institutionalized military provided by an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– Yes

Notes: The military apparatus of the Inca State would have protected the state religion and its institutions from any external threats.

Written Language

Does the religious group in question possess its own distinct written language:

– No

Notes: The Incas did not possess a written language in the European sense (i.e. the recording of speech using graphical signs or marks). However, they recorded a great deal of information on the quipu (or khipu), which were knotted pieces of string made of wool and cotton. However, the quipu recorded all information using number strings (somewhat comparable to the use of binary coding in modern computers). As such, the quipu did not record the Inca's spoken language, nor the spoken language of any other Andean group.

Is a non-religion-specific written language available to the group's adherents through an

institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– No

Notes: The Incas did not possess a written language in the European sense (i.e. the recording of speech using graphical signs or marks). However, they recorded a great deal of information on the quipu (or khipu), which were knotted pieces of string made of wool and cotton. However, the quipu recorded all information using number strings (somewhat comparable to the use of binary coding in modern computers). As such, the quipu did not record the Inca's spoken language, nor the spoken language of any other Andean group

Is a non-religion-specific written language used by the group's adherents through an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– No

Notes: The Incas did not possess a written language in the European sense (i.e. the recording of speech using graphical signs or marks). However, they recorded a great deal of information on the quipu (or khipu), which were knotted pieces of string made of wool and cotton. However, the quipu recorded all information using number strings (somewhat comparable to the use of binary coding in modern computers). As such, the quipu did not record the Inca's spoken language, nor the spoken language of any other Andean group.

Calendar

Does the religious group in question possess a formal calendar:

– Yes

Notes: The Incas made use of both a solar and lunar calendar, and seem to have made attempts to integrate them, although the precise details of this integration are debated by modern scholars. It is known that they subdivided the year into twelve named lunar months, and then corrected annually for the discrepancy between the lunar and solar cycles. The cyclical movements of the planet Venus, and some stars, especially the Pleiades, were also recognized and ritually marked by the Incas. Although the months were based on lunar cycles, it seems the most important religious ceremonies were tied to the solar cycle. In particular, the important festivals of Inti Raymi and Qhapaq Raymi were associated with the summer and winter solstices respectively.

Is a formal calendar provided for the group's adherents by an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– Yes

Notes: The formal calendar of the Inca state religion was indistinguishable from the calendar used by the Inca State and Inca society in general.

Food Production

Does the religious group in question provide food for themselves:

– No

Notes: Religious institutions in the Inca Empire were dependent on the state and its taxation powers for food resources; they would not have been able to feed themselves without this direct state support.

Is food provided to the group's adherents by an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– Yes

Notes: Religious institutions in the Inca State were dependent on food resources obtained via taxation.

Please characterize the forms/levels of food production [choose all that apply]:

- Fishing
- Patoralism
- Small-scale agriculture / horticultural gardens or orchards
- Large-scale agriculture (e.g., monocropping, organized irrigation systems)

Notes: The Inca State organized agricultural production in a large scale, especially focused on the cultivation of maize (as a source of calories) and of coca leaf (as a stimulant). State farms and royal estates were the most centralized and complex forms of food production in the empire, entailing significant mono-cropping and employing thousands of workers. Local communities would have organized their own agriculture on a smaller scale, often including smaller garden plots and community fields. In certain areas, especially around lake Titicaca and on the Pacific coasts, fishing would have been an important source of calories as well. In the higher-elevation grasslands of the Andes, camelids would have been herded—especially in the Altiplano region. According to some ethnohistoric accounts, the royal herds of the Incas numbered around a million animals. Local communities would have had their own, much more modest, herds of llamas and alpacas.

Bibliography

General References

Reference: Inca, D'Altroy, Terence N.. *The Incas*. 2nd ed.. Wiley Blackwell, 2014.

Reference: Inca, Classen, Constance. "Aesthetics and Asceticism in Inca Religion" 32, no. 1 (1990). <https://doi.org/10.2307/25605560>.

Reference: Inca, Bauer, Brian. *The Ritual Landscape of the Inca*. Edited by Sonia Alconini and Alan Covey. Oxford University Press, 2018. <https://doi.org/10.1093/oxfordhb/9780190219352.013.6>.

Reference: Inca, Ceruti, Maria Constanza. "Frozen Mummies from Andean Mountaintop Shrines: Bioarchaeology and Ethnohistory of Inca Human Sacrifice" 2015 (2015). <https://doi.org/10.1155/2015/439428>.

Reference: Inca, Dean, Carolyn. *A Culture of Stone: Inka Perspectives on Rock*. Durham: Duke University Press, 2010.

Reference: Inca, Niles, Susan. "The Nature of Inca Royal Estates". In *Machu Picchu: Unveiling the Mystery of the Incas*, edited by Richard Burger and Lucy Salazar, 49–68. New Haven: Yale University Press, 2004.

Reference: Inca, Gose, Peter. "Oracles, Divine Kingship, and Political Representation in the Inka State" 43, no. 1 (1996). <https://doi.org/10.2307/483342>.

Reference: Inca, Bray, Tamara L., ed.. *The Archaeology of Wak'as: Explorations of the Sacred in the Pre-columbian Andes*. Edited by Tamara L. Bray. University Press of Colorado, 2015. <https://doi.org/10.5876/9781607323181>.

